

1 Supplementary file

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Evolution and biomineralization of pteropod shells

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39 **Table S1** Information about sample taxonomy, collection and origins.

Species	Suborder	Superfamily	Family	Location	Sample origin
<i>Diacria costata</i>	Euthecosomata	Cavolinioidea	Cavoliniidae	22°34.4N, 157°40.8W	North Pacific, Hawaii (KOK1703)
<i>Diacavolinia longirostris</i>	Euthecosomata	Cavolinioidea	Cavoliniidae		
<i>Styliola subula</i>	Euthecosomata	Cavolinioidea	Creseidae	Surface sediments from the Caribbean Sea offshore of Montserrat	
<i>Creseis acicula</i>	Euthecosomata	Cavolinioidea	Creseidae		
<i>Limacina helicina antarctica</i>	Euthecosomata	Limacinoidea	Limacinidae	40°07.0035S, 30°54.8200W 41°28.648S, 33°51.519W	South Atlantic (AMT24)
<i>Heliconoides inflatus</i>	Euthecosomata	Limacinoidea	Heliconoididae	41°9.57282S, 30°0.29436W	South Atlantic (AMT27)
<i>Peracle moluccensis</i>	Pseudothechosomata	Cymbulioidea	Peraclidae	44°48.048N, 14°51.348W	North Atlantic (AMT27)
<i>Peracle valdiviae</i>	Pseudothechosomata	Cymbulioidea	Peraclidae	14°12.3774N, 27°55.7259W	North Atlantic (AMT24)

<i>Heliconoides mercinensis</i> † (Watelet and Lefèvre, 1880)	Euthecosomata	Limacinoidea	Heliconoididae	RGM.515524 St. Gobain (France, Aisne department), railroad cut between St. Gobain and Biribis. Eocene, Ypresian, Sables de Cuise Coll. A.W. Janssen, July 21, 1985.
<i>Altaspiratella bearnensis</i> † (Curry, 1982)	Euthecosomata	Limacinoidea	Limacinidae	RGM.229304 and RGM.396617 Clay pit of tuilerie Lartigue & Dumas, Gan (France, Atlantic Pyrenees); Marnes de Gan Formation, Eocene, Ypresian, nannoplankton zone† top NP 12 to NP 13
<i>Camptoceratops priscus</i> † (Godwin-Austen, 1882)	Euthecosomata	Cavolinioidea	Creseidae	
<i>Heliconoides tertiaria</i> † (Tate, 1887)	Euthecosomata	Limacinoidea	Heliconoididae	RGM.229472 Muddy Creek, near Hamilton (Australia, Victoria) Miocene, Balcombian to Bairnsdalian, Muddy Creek Formation (~ Langhian) Coll. D. Curry, donated June 1987

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Cavolinioida

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Limacinoidea

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Fossil pteropods

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61 **Figure S1** Overview of the pteropod species examined in this study. Shell locations
 62 imaged by SEM are marked with white squares and numbered in order of appearance
 63 in Figures 2-5. NA, location not available.

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80 **Supplementary methods**

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82 **Microstructure analyses (Figures 2, 3, 4 and 5)**

83 Shells of *Diacria costata*, *Diacavolinia longirostris*, *Creseis acicula*, *Syliola subula*,
84 *Heliconoides inflatus*, *Limacina helicina antarctica*, *Peracle moluccensis* and *Peracle*
85 *valdiviae* were air dried overnight at 37 °C. Fresh cuts were randomly made using a
86 needle on the shell surfaces. For polished cuts the shells were embedded in LR White
87 Medium resin (London Resin). Prior to use, benzoyl peroxide (catalyst) was dissolved
88 in the LR White resin monomer solution (9.9 g per 500 mL) for 24 h, under constant
89 stirring, at room temperature. A first layer of resin was introduced in Eppendorf's and
90 polymerized at 60 °C. Specimens were laid in different positions in the first layer and
91 immersed in a second layer being under vacuum for 30 min and transferred again to
92 60 °C to allow for the polymerization to proceed (one night to two days). Cross sections
93 of the solid resin were prepared using a cross sectioning Leica sp1600 saw microtome.
94 Mirror polishing of the cross sections was made using a Minitech 233 with 0.05 µm
95 aluminium oxide paste and grinding disks of P320, P600, P 1200, P4000. Polished
96 surfaces were etched with EDTA 1% (from 30 s to 1 min, depending on shell thickness)
97 rinsed with distilled water and dried. All samples were sputter coated with gold using
98 a DII-29030SCTR (Smart Coater). Microstructures were observed with a Hitachi TM-
99 1000 tabletop scanning electron microscope (SEM) under a fixed acceleration voltage
100 of 15 kV, in back-scattered electron mode, without carbon sputtering belonging to
101 Laboratoire Biogéosciences UMR CNRS 6282 of the University of Burgundy-Franche-
102 Comté. More detailed observations were performed with a Field Emission Gun
103 Scanning Electron Microscope (JEOL, JSM-7600 F) under an acceleration voltage of
104 5 kV or with a SEM (JEOL, JSM-6480LV) under an acceleration voltage of 10 kV, at
105 Naturalis Biodiversity Center.

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107 **Homology searches (Figure 6)**

108 Collection of shell matrix proteins (SMPs): Two sets of gastropod SMPs were collected
109 from the closest relatives to pteropods with characterized shell proteomes
110 (Heterobranchia), and merged. The sets consisted of 59 predicted proteins from
111 *Cepaea nemoralis* (Mann and Jackson, 2014) and 48 predicted proteins from *Lymnaea*
112 *stagnalis* (Herlitzke et al., 2018). The final list of SMPs was reduced by removing
113 “redundant” (or highly similar sequences) using Cd-Hit (Li and Godzik, 2006), with a
114 cutoff of 90% identity resulting in 99 sequences considered as representative and non-
115 redundant.

116 Collection and assessment of proteomes from pteropods and outgroups: sequenced

117 transcriptomes from the adult stage of 25 pteropod species were selected in
118 combination with three outgroups (Zapata et al., 2014), including the proteome of
119 *Aplysia californica*, predicted from the draft genome assembly version from May 2013
120 as described in (Peijnenburg et al., 2020). In brief, after quality assessment of the
121 reads with fastqc, all transcriptomes were assembled with Trinity (v2.3.2) (Haas et al.,
122 2013) and processed to avoid cross-contamination and redundancy due to splice
123 variants. For each non-redundant transcript, the best open reading frame (ORF) and
124 protein translation was obtained with TransDecoder (<https://transdecoder.github.io>)
125 using BLASTP against a version of Swiss-Prot limited to metazoan taxa (e-value 10^{-5}).
126 In order to provide a better understanding and interpretation of the results obtained
127 from the homology searches, the assessment of gene content and completeness of
128 the protein gene sets was performed with BUSCO (version 4.1.2) using the pre-defined
129 metazoan Benchmarking set of Universal Single-Copy Orthologs with 954 evolutionary
130 conserved orthologous groups (Simão et al., 2015; Waterhouse et al., 2018) (Table
131 S2).

132 Data analysis: For each transcriptome or proteome we performed homology searches
133 against the molluscan SMPs using BLASP (cut-off: 35% identity, 75% SMPs
134 coverage). The number of transcripts matching each SMP were represented in a
135 matrix (Table S3) and combined with the pteropod time-calibrated phylogenomic tree
136 described in (Peijnenburg et al., 2020). Profiles of transcript abundance were
137 visualized with Evolview (Zhang et al., 2012).

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141 **Supplementary references**

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